

Enhancing States' Compliance with International Legal Obligations and Victims of SGBV's Access to Reparations: Setting Legal Precedents for an Effective Remedy under International Law

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The paper examines the potential implications of state responsibility for breaching international obligations, particularly those related to protecting and ensuring respect for the rights enshrined in international human rights law. It identifies an opportunity to redress victims of sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) crimes through the principle of state responsibility as an alternative to individual criminal responsibility. Employing a doctrinal research approach and analysing case law alongside international humanitarian and human rights instruments, the study concludes that the criminalisation of individuals responsible for SGBV is inadequate. The current prevalence of SGBV contrasts with the increasing international recognition that SGBV during peacetime violates fundamental principles of international humanitarian and human rights. It further suggests that the principles of state responsibility are firmly established in international law and should apply equally to cases involving SGBV. More significantly, holding the state responsible for SGBV committed by public and private actors is more effective and encouraging than individual criminal responsibility, potentially leading to greater compliance with international legal obligations and enhancing victims' access to reparations. Thus, the paper's analysis extends beyond merely questioning whether states' obligations to protect and ensure respect for women's human rights have been violated and what the consequences are. Rather, it aims to analyse international law sources imposing obligations on states, the violation of which may entail a duty to provide reparation to victims, including compensation, rehabilitation, and guarantees of non-repetition. This approach aligns with the principles set forth by the International Law Commission on state responsibility for wrongful acts.

Keywords: International law, gender-based, sexual, violence, victims, state responsibility.

Unlike the rule on civil liability, which requires physical damage, the principle of state responsibility is more focused on wrongful acts. Sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) crimes persist at an immense, almost overwhelming scale. Unfortunately, this issue has existed since the dawn of human civilisation, and its recognition as an infringement of international human rights law has gained international acknowledgement (Hasselbacher, 2009). Sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) encompasses various types of violent behaviour perpetrated without the consent of the victims based on their gender (UNHCR, 2021). These harmful acts include emotional, psychological, and physical abuse, as well as serious physical harm that can even lead to death (ICRC, 2002). SGBV can be perpetrated by and against anyone, but generally, perpetrators are predominantly men, and victims are largely women and girls (WHO, 2021). The social construction of gender and the power dynamics of gender roles within society are among the key structural drivers of gender-based violence and femicide (Skrla, 2000). Various social, cultural, economic, political, and legal factors have compounded

SGBV (Wies et al., 2018). SGBV manifests in an assortment of harmful acts, including Rape, Partner Violence (IPV), Sexual Assault, Sexual and Gender-Based Violence, Gender-Based Violence, Violence Against Women and Interpersonal Violence, Domestic Violence, and Collective Sexual Violence. All these acts are understood differently and may occur under varying circumstances. For instance, IPV is variously defined, such as “a form of interpersonal violence by a spouse or life partner” (Shumba, 2017) or “violence committed against a woman by her current or former spouse or boyfriend” (Horn, 2010) or “violence committed in a present or past relationship” (Manuel, 2019). Unlike IPV, which can have differing definitions depending on the source, rape, as one of the most studied forms of SGBV, is generally defined as “An act done which causes penetration of one person's genital organs with the genital organs of another without their consent or where the consent is obtained by force, threats or intimidation of any kind.” Sexual assault (SA) similarly contains elements akin to rape. It is defined as “any genital, oral, or anal penetration by a part of the accused's body or by an object using force or without the victim's consent” (Ononge, 2005). Both require the consent of the victim, and the distinction between the two is insubstantial, especially considering sexual assault as “rape, attempted rape, sexual abuse and sexual exploitation,” or as “all non-consenting sexual activity from fondling to penetration” (Amenu & Hiko, 2014; Krolkowski & Koyfman, 2012). Sexual and gender-based violence also includes Sexual Violence, generally referred to as “a serious societal problem that creates significant challenges to local communities.” Gatuguta

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et al. (2018) characterises sexual violence as “a serious global health problem with significant physical, psychological, and social consequences.” Unlike all other forms of violence, violence against women is generally viewed in conflict settings, primarily because it is an all-encompassing term that can cover many other types of violence, including rape, forced prostitution, and sexual slavery. Violence against women is also more commonly associated with humanitarian efforts than other terms, such as SV or IPV (Liebling et al., 2020a). Accordingly, VAW is often not explicitly defined but rather described as a “weapon of war” and a “growing problem during armed conflict” (Liebling et al., 2020a, 2020b). A more comprehensive definition of violence against women is found in the Protocol to the African Charter on the Rights of Women in Africa, known as the Maputo Protocol. The Protocol defines Violence against Women as “all acts perpetrated against women which cause or could cause them physical, sexual, psychological, and economic harm, including the threat to take such acts; or to undertake the imposition of arbitrary restrictions on or deprivation of fundamental freedoms in private or public life in peacetime and during situations of armed conflict or war” (Maputo Protocol, 2003). The definition of VAW in the Maputo Protocol comprises all the legal elements or acts of violence against women. It considers not only physical acts but also psychological, economic, and even the threat of such acts. More importantly, it considers the deprivation of fundamental freedoms such as freedom of movement, expression, and association as part of violence against women (Maputo Protocol, 2003). To an extent, the Maputo Protocol also encompasses SGBV, including harmful traditional practices such as female genital mutilation (FGM) and underage marriage, as well as the stigma and bias faced by SGBV victims. The sphere and location of these acts are no longer a matter of contention, whether in armed conflict or in times of peace, and whether committed in public or private life. Such private acts include Interpersonal Violence, Domestic Violence, and Collective Sexual Violence. Collective Sexual Violence refers to non-consensual sexual activity by a group of individuals or a single individual driven by social movement goals (Ten Benschel & Sample, 2017; Zraly et al., 2011) while domestic and interpersonal violence serve as an umbrella term encompassing community violence, IPV, SV, and more (Decker et al., 2018). In times of peace, sexual and gender-based violence is perpetuated in both private and public places (WHO, 2021). Victims face physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence (IPV) or non-partner sexual violence. Therefore, it is clear that violence against women is an evolving concept that includes all acts of sexual and gender-based violence occurring both during conflict and in times of peace.

The international law perspective on SGBV is also praiseworthy. International law defines Gender-based violence (GBV) as harmful acts that include emotional, psychological, and physical abuse, as well as sexual violence (SV), directed against a person based on their gender (Phyu Phyu, 2024). These harmful acts are perpetrated primarily by men against women and girls (Applin et al., 2023). They are widely ascribed to the norms embodied in international humanitarian and conventional law, whether as crimes against humanity, war crimes, or genocide (de Koningh, 2023). Consequently, the norm embodied in these crimes is part of the highest norm of *jus cogens* for which the violation is not permitted (Khan, 2023). Violence against women (VAW) and gender-based violence (GBV) have a long history under international law (Chinkin, 1994). Hoefler and Fearon (2014) note that “physical

violence in societies is a much larger and more pervasive phenomenon than just civil war violence”. The current prevalence stands in contrast to increased international recognition that intimate partner violence (IPV) or non-partner (NSV), including rape, domestic violence, sexual slavery, and other forms of sexual violence, whether in peacetimes and during armed conflict; in private or public domain, violates fundamental principles of international human rights and humanitarian law (Marochkin, 2014). SGBV is a major obstacle to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Okpokwasili, 2024). This is obvious given the growing number of concerns about progress toward the realisation of the Sustainable Development Goals 5, 11, and 16. These goals include a specific target to “eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres.

Not only do its contexts differ depending on whether in times of conflict or in times of peace, but also the crimes of sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) remain a significant challenge for many states around the world (Amnesty International, 2018). This is illustrated by the most recently publicised cases of systematic and widespread sexual and gender-based violence perpetrated in many countries, including the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), South Africa, and South Sudan. South Africa is often considered the economic powerhouse of Africa and has one of the highest rates of gender-based violence (GBV) globally. The South African government has declared GBV a national crisis, with figures showing alarmingly high rates of sexual assault and intimate partner violence (Enaifoghe, 2021). According to a 2018 report by the South African Police Service, there were over 40,000 reported cases of rape in a single year (South African Police Service Crime Statistics, 2018; Machisa, 2023). However, many experts believe the true figure is much higher due to underreporting (Luyt, 2008). Studies indicate that one in five South African women has experienced some form of sexual violence (Ajayi, 2021). Although the causes of SGBV in South Africa are multifaceted, stemming from historical, social, and economic factors, efforts to combat SGBV have been varied (Omotoso, 2022). Efforts include enacting laws such as the Protection from Harassment Act 17 of 2011, the Domestic Violence Act, and the Sexual Offences Act. Despite significant strides in policy development, their implementation remains inconsistent (Ncube, 2021). Likewise, the government's attempts to increase police sensitivity to GBV and to provide more support for survivors through services such as shelters and counselling remain inconsistent (Abrahams, 2004). Coupled with the above challenges are institutional failures, corruption, and inadequate training for law enforcement and judicial personnel, which often result in low conviction rates and poor outcomes of redress.

Unlike in South Africa, in the Democratic Republic of Congo, sexual and gender-based violence is a particularly egregious and tragic aspect of the ongoing conflict in the country. The DRC has been grappling with wars, rebellions, and civil wars for decades and has claimed the lives of almost twelve million people, excluding displaced persons. Particularly in the eastern regions, where armed groups, military forces, and rebel factions backed by the Rwandese Government regularly commit acts of SGBV as part of their warfare strategy (Kidanu, 2024). The use of rape as a weapon of war has been well-documented, with women and girls subjected to systemic sexual violence by soldiers and militias (Baaz, 2013). According to the United Nations, the DRC has one of the highest rates of sexual

violence in conflict in the world (Pratt, 2004). It is estimated that over 800,000 women have been raped since the war began in the late 1990s, and the complete lack of infrastructure in many areas, including health services, legal protections, and social support for survivors, compounds the scale of violence (Brown, 2011). Many women are displaced by conflict and are thus left vulnerable to sexual violence, both in refugee camps and on the move (van Wieringen, 2020). The complex interplay between armed conflict, the lack of legitimacy of political actors and their institutions, societal structures, and inadequate governance contributes to conflicts that cause SGBV in the DRC (Mugisho et al., 2022). The arrogance and envy of neighbouring countries such as Rwanda and Uganda for natural resources have always justified the presence of their army groups operating with total impunity in the country (Reid, 2009). Cultural factors such as gender inequality, coupled with the widespread breakdown of law and order in many regions, mean that women are often seen as targets, and the violations of their rights go unpunished (van Wieringen, 2020). These two countries paint a dark picture of how states' failure contributes to the predicaments of women and girls in times of conflict and peace. This is not to undermine national and international efforts, such as the International Criminal Court's prosecution of warlords for crimes of sexual violence (Koepp, 2020). The major challenge with existing criminal mechanisms is holding countless perpetrators accountable and ensuring reparations for survivors. Consequently, only national mechanisms can take the bulk of cases and ensure that perpetrators do not escape responsibility. Failure by the governments to take appropriate measures will entrench impunity for perpetrators. Likewise, many women in remote and conflict-affected areas remain unreachable, and the challenge of reintegrating survivors into society, providing them with education, and restoring their economic livelihoods is among the issues that call for effective remedies under international law. The question is whether the international pronouncements on violence against women and gender-based violence in times of peace have been exuberant and praiseworthy, particularly when considering sexual and gender-based violence as a violation of international human rights laws. Despite the strides made through criminal accountability and the adoption of human rights instruments (Aoláin-Ní et al., 2011). Criticisms for the tragic failure of the international legal order to adequately address VAW and GBV continue to rise (Bunch, 1994; Cole, 2010). These criticisms range from the presence of strong procedural and evidentiary protections for the accused or perpetrators, to a perpetrator-oriented approach, to a lack of or insufficient gendered approaches, to a limited ability to protect victims' identities, physical security, and psychological health (Jordan et al., 2010; Dixon, 2002). Even more alarming than the structural and procedural limits, international accountability mechanisms have a limited capacity to address the vast majority of sexual and gender-based violence, both in times of peace and during conflicts (Altunjan, 2021). Consequently, national prosecutions are in a position to take on a bulk of cases, as international mechanisms can only take a handful (McDougall, 2000). Despite legal protection in most countries of the world, violence remains pervasive due to weak enforcement of these policies (Mikton, 2014). The failure by states to ensure effective implementation or adherence to the legal instruments and policies constitutes a mere violation of one or more of its obligations, including the obligation to enact legislation, if not yet done so, the duty to investigate, if sufficient evidence exists, the duty to extradite

or to submit to prosecution, and if found guilty, the duty to punish (UNGA A/RES/60/147). The question is whether there are international norms protecting SGBV for which the violation may incur a state's responsibility under international law. Also, the question of whether a state is directly responsible for the acts of sexual and gender-based violence carried out publicly or privately by individuals hastens the need for this research (Klugman, 2017). It is therefore expedient to examine governments' responsibilities as a remedy for redressing victims of SGBV in times of peace. The government's failures to promote, protect and ensure respect for the rights of women and girls constitute a plea to ascertain the government's responsibility for the breach of international obligations. The extent to which rules on the enforcement of customary international and conventional laws constitute an alternative route for victims' redress has not been sufficiently explored. This research suggests that an effective victim's redress mechanism under international law requires both criminal accountability for the perpetrators and the state's civil responsibility. However, the latter is more promising because it is more likely to increase states' willingness to take their international legal obligations, including those regarding victims' rights to reparation, more seriously. The research posits that principles of state responsibility under international law serve as a critical tool for ensuring effective remedies for victims of sexual and gender-based violence. Thus, the question of how and to what extent the rule of customary international and conventional laws constitutes an alternative route to redress victims of sexual and gender-based crimes has hastened the need for this paper. In support of this case, the paper offers two overlapping arguments that make such a conclusion foreseeable. Firstly, international law enjoins states to respect, ensure respect for, and promote the provisions of international treaties they have willingly accepted. One such obligation is to respect, protect, fulfil and promote the rights of people (SERAC Case, 2001). These obligations extend beyond mere non-interference; they require proactive measures to realise rights. Non-compliance with these obligations means that a state must incur its international responsibility. This responsibility arises because of the omission or failure by the government or officials to prevent sexual and gender-based violence or failure to exercise due diligence to ensure respect for women's dignity or honour and physical integrity.

The paper seeks not to determine whether states' obligations to enact and enforce legislative, administrative, social, and economic measures, to prohibit, prevent, and punish all forms of violence against women, and to establish mechanisms for the rehabilitation of women have been violated and what are the consequences, but rather to analyse international law sources that place obligations on states, the violation of which may give rise to the obligation to cease and make reparation. The paper, therefore, proceeds in two parts. After the introduction, part one will review international frameworks for protecting victims of SGBV and define the state's obligations. The paper will then assess current and proposed international rules and regulations that provide for effective victim redress in cases of SGBV. As Ago (1970) correctly put it: '... It is one thing to define a rule and the content of the obligation it imposes, and another to determine whether that obligation has been violated and what the consequences of the violation are.' Thus, the paper will focus on the role of international law in providing a safe and secure environment for victims of SGBV.

International Legal Frameworks and State Duties in Addressing Sexual and Gender-based Violence

Sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) is a widespread global issue that transcends cultural, religious, social, and geographic boundaries (Fader, 2020). Despite its persistent occurrence throughout human history, the international legal community has long recognised the need to prohibit such violence. Early international legal instruments, such as the Control Council Law No. 10 (1945), explicitly addressed rape, while the London and Tokyo Charters (1946) included references to “other inhumane acts.” These early efforts laid the foundation for the progressive development of legal norms in international humanitarian law.

The 1949 Geneva Conventions and the 1977 Additional Protocols further codified protections, particularly for women during armed conflict. Article 27 of the Fourth Geneva Convention and Article 76 of Additional Protocol I expressly prohibit acts that violate a woman's dignity, including rape, forced prostitution, and any form of indecent assault. Article 75 of Protocol I affirms the humane treatment of all individuals without discrimination and underlines the obligation of warring parties to respect personal dignity and religious practices (AP I, 1977). It also emphasises the need to protect family unity and offer special protections for women. This article forms a comprehensive basis for the protection of women against sexual violence across all times and locations, regardless of conflict status.

Although international protection of humanitarian law (IHL) and international human rights law (IHRL) serve distinct purposes, one applies primarily during armed conflict and the other at all times, their mutual reinforcement has contributed to the evolution of binding legal obligations (Prokhorenko et al., 2022). These obligations are embedded in various core human rights treaties, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966), the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (1965), and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW, 1979). Article 6 of CEDAW mandates that states take legislative and other measures to combat trafficking in women and exploitation through prostitution. Similarly, Article 5(b) of the ICERD guarantees protection from violence regardless of the perpetrator's identity (ICERD, 1966).

The Maputo Protocol (2003) which supplements the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, advances a continental framework for addressing SGBV. Article 4 guarantees every woman the right to life, dignity, and protection from inhumane and degrading treatment, explicitly condemning all forms of exploitation and cruelty. This Protocol provides both definitional clarity and enforcement mechanisms for addressing sexual violence across Africa. Article 1(j) defines violence against women as “all acts perpetrated against women which cause or could cause them physical, sexual, psychological, and economic harm, including the threat to take such acts; or to undertake the imposition of arbitrary restrictions on or deprivation of fundamental freedoms in private or public life in peace time and during situations of armed conflicts or war” (Maputo Protocol, 2003). SGBV encompasses a broad spectrum of harm, including physical, psychological, emotional, and economic abuse. All these elements translate the view that the international criminal legal regime of SGBV has evolved. The Rome

Statute of the International Criminal Court (2002) lists acts such as rape, sexual slavery, forced pregnancy, and enforced sterilisation under crimes against humanity (Article 7). The ICC's Elements of Crimes document recognises rape as a primary form of SGBV. The jurisprudence of international criminal tribunals, notably the ICTY and ICTR, has significantly shaped the legal landscape. In the landmark Akayesu case (ICTR-96-4-T, 1998) the ICTR recognised rape and sexual violence as acts of genocide when systematically committed with the intent to destroy a particular group. Importantly, Akayesu was held responsible not for directly committing these crimes, but for failing to prevent them, affirming the principle of due diligence for state actors. The judgment expanded the legal understanding of rape to encompass acts driven by power and coercion, not merely physical force. Despite these advances, SGBV remains one of the least prosecuted crimes under international criminal law. Barriers to investigation, prosecution, and victim reparations persist (Women's Initiatives for Gender Justice, 2011). Therefore, rethinking the adjudication framework is essential for ensuring accountability and justice.

State Responsibilities under International Law in the Context of SGBV

Even with the normative foundation provided by international human rights instruments, SGBV against women continues in both peacetime and conflict. International law imposes obligations on states to take comprehensive actions against such violence. These include enacting legislation, investigating and prosecuting perpetrators, and, when appropriate, extraditing or trying them (as required under Article 49 of the Geneva Convention I). UN General Assembly Resolution 60/147 reinforces the responsibility of states to provide legal, administrative, and other measures to protect women from violence and ensure access to justice and effective remedies. States are expected to adopt national laws prohibiting all forms of SGBV, physical, sexual, psychological, and economic. These laws should also cover indirect forms of violence, such as threats or coercive restrictions. International instruments such as the ICCPR (Article 2(2)) and CAT (Article 12) require states to take proactive steps, including investigating, arresting, prosecuting or extraditing offenders. States must establish judicial and administrative bodies capable of providing legal remedies (CAT, 1987). Moreover, these institutions must be independent, well-resourced, and trained to handle SGBV cases with sensitivity and efficiency. For example, Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights underscores the right to a fair and impartial hearing. Importantly, international law allows for universal jurisdiction in cases of SGBV, meaning that offenders may be prosecuted outside their home countries. While extradition is subject to conditions, it remains a vital alternative when local prosecution is not feasible (Article 3 of the CAT). In addition to enacting and enforcing criminal laws, states must ensure that penalties are proportionate to the severity of the crime. Incorporating these provisions into domestic law deters future offences and empowers victims to challenge state inaction. This principle aligns with the foundational criminal law doctrines of *nullum crimen sine lege* and *nulla poena sine lege* (no crime or punishment without law). Ultimately, the international legal obligations of states to legislate, investigate, prosecute, or extradite offenders, and to provide victim redress, form the backbone of state accountability and the operationalisation of victims' rights to effective remedies. In interpreting the content and scope of such

obligations, whether under national or international law, judicial reasoning must be guided by widely accepted jurisprudence and foundational principles. Notably, the *SERAC* case and the UN's *Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law* serve as essential frameworks for understanding the substantive and operational dimensions of states' positive obligations (SERA Case, 2001). In the *SERAC* case, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights explained the levels of state duty to protect and promote international human rights law (SERAC, 2001). The obligation to respect, protect, fulfil and promote the rights of people. These obligations extend beyond mere non-interference; they require proactive measures to realise rights. In protecting and promoting the rights of victims of SGBV, governments must refrain from interfering directly with women's rights or indirectly by preventing private individuals from interfering with the enjoyment of women's rights. In *Urgenda v. The State of the Netherlands*, the courts held that Articles 2 and 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) impose positive obligations on the Dutch state (Urgenda Case, 2002). Full compliance with international obligations by states means that states must take appropriate and effective measures, including avoiding direct or indirect encroachments on individuals' fundamental rights, including their autonomy, freedoms, and access to essential resources. This obligation entails a due diligence standard, requiring the state to demonstrate that it has taken reasonable and timely steps to prevent foreseeable harm. In practice, protection entails the creation and maintenance of a legal and institutional environment, through a coherent system of laws and regulations that enables individuals to fully realise their rights and freedoms (Krysztof, 1999). It also means that states must punish the perpetrators of violence and implement programs for the rehabilitation of women victims. The second argument, therefore, is the legal consequence of states' internationally wrongful acts. The breach of an international obligation implies states' obligations to cease wrongful conduct and to make full reparation for the damages caused. More exasperating is that the rules on the enforcement of sexual and gender-based violence are part of peremptory norms of customary and conventional international law for which the breach by the State entails aggravated consequences.

Remedies under International Law for Sexual and Gender-based Violence

A breach of an international obligation and law by a State entails its international responsibility (ILC, 2022). In other words, non-compliance by a state means a state must incur its international responsibility. Like in the case of *Akayesu*, the state's responsibility arises because of the omission or failure of the government or the officials to respect and ensure respect for women's rights, protect women and girls against violence, and prevent sexual and gender-based violence during the genocide (*Akayesu*, Case No. ICTR-96-4-T, 1998). Thus, the failure to exercise due diligence, to ensure respect for women's dignity, honour, and physical integrity, constitutes the basis for conceptualising victims' redress under international law.

The gap between criminal prosecutions and victims' redress can be addressed by applying rules on state responsibility for internationally wrongful acts. The application of the principle of

international law requires a breach of international law by a State to entail its international responsibility (ILC, 2022). This is a basic principle of international law, which is established as a norm of customary international law (Wyler, 2002). The general or basic rules of international law concerning the responsibility of states for their internationally wrongful acts are set in the Draft Code Articles on State Responsibility. The Draft Code establishes primary and secondary rules on state responsibility. The difference between general or secondary rules and primary rules is that the former define general conditions under international law for a State to be considered responsible for wrongful actions or omissions, and the legal consequences that flow from them (ILC, 2022). Unlike secondary rules, primary rules on state responsibility define the content of the international obligations for which the violation gives rise to state responsibility. Basically, whether there is a breach of international law depends on two requirements: the legal framework prohibiting the act and the obligation alleged to have been breached under international law (ILC, 2022). These rules are codified in customary international law, as discussed above. State responsibility for acts of sexual and gender-based violence, therefore, arises because of the failure to comply with treaty obligations on the protection and promotion of the rights of women. The state incurs its international responsibility regardless of the legal connection between the perpetrator and the state (A/RES/60/147, 2001). With few exceptions, the prosecutorial records of states' responsibility for sexual and gender-based violence both in peacetimes and during armed conflict indicate an under-enforcement of international law (Ni Aolain, 2014). State responsibility can serve as an effective remedy within national and international accountability mechanisms. The requirement under international law for attribution of acts performed by individuals to the state is that the state must exercise control over the individuals, whether by giving them specific instructions or by exercising overall control when the individuals are organised (*Tadic* case - ICTY 1999). The level of control varied depending on whether the individuals were acting *de jure* or *de facto*. *De facto*, responsibility is attributed to the state to prevent it from escaping responsibility when using private individuals. It appears that attributing violations of international human rights and humanitarian law to individuals is an exception to the rule of state responsibility under international law. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) in the *Nicaragua* case (Merits) stated that to be responsible for a violation of international human rights and humanitarian law, a state would have to have "effective control" over the activities in the course of which the violations occurred. This approach was used after WWII, when the Japanese government was held responsible for Japan's system of military sexual slavery during WWII (Chinkin, 2001). Relevant is the fact that the Japanese government's responsibility arises from the failure of most legal actions in both national and international forums. Particularly, the failure by the Japanese legislature to enact appropriate legislation or the failure by the Japanese government to acknowledge crimes under international law committed against women, including crimes of "sexual slavery, rape and other forms of sexual violence, failure to prosecute those responsible for the "comfort system," and failure to establish an official grant of monetary or other reparations. The Women's Tribunal had jurisdiction over individuals involved in planning, committing, or concealing violations either directly or via command. It also exercised its jurisdiction over state responsibility to find that the

individual crimes against humanity were attributable to the government of Japan because they were committed by government agents and because the government failed to prevent or punish the perpetrators. The state of Japan was also found responsible because of the continued violations of victims' rights arising from its concealment of documents regarding the crimes of sexual slavery; failure to issue a genuine apology, and failure to punish those responsible, or provide official compensation. The state was also responsible for the continued opposition to efforts to obtain reparations in its national courts, and failure to counteract revisionist claims that "comfort women" were voluntary prostitutes (Women's International War Crimes Tribunal, 2001). As stated above, the principle of due diligence is a cornerstone of state responsibility in this domain, requiring states to exercise appropriate care to prevent SGBV, protect victims, and prosecute perpetrators. This standard has evolved from general human rights obligations into a specific benchmark for evaluating state compliance with international law on gender-based violence. The due diligence requirement encompasses both immediate response obligations when violence occurs and systemic preventive measures designed to address the root causes and structural factors that enable SGBV to persist. The imposition of liability on the state for the failure to protect or prevent human rights violations is not new under international law (ILC, 2001). State practice has established this rule as a norm of customary international law and a principle of international law. Any breach of an engagement involves an obligation to make reparation. Reparation is an indispensable attribute or consequence of any responsibility (Eichmann case, 1961; Germany's Federal Supreme Court, 1963; Netherlands, District Court of Hague, 1949; ICTY Furundzija, 1998; TADIC, 1999). This is a basic rule of international law: reparation is compulsory for any violation of international law, and there is no need to incorporate this requirement into any treaty. A state responsible for the violation is under an obligation to make full reparation for the injury caused by the internationally wrongful act' (Art. 31, ILC 2001). The Draft Articles on State Responsibility provide various forms of reparation, including restitution, compensation, or satisfaction (Art. 34, ILC 2001). Whether single or combined, reparation measures need to be determined on a case-by-case basis. Likewise, international law provides that state responsibility may exist in addition to the requirements for prosecuting individuals for gross violations (Art. 2 ICCPR, 1966). This is armoured in Article 40 of the Draft Articles on State Responsibility. "... a breach of such an obligation is serious if it involves a gross or systematic failure by the responsible State to fulfil the obligation." In the context of sexual and gender-based violence, a state's failure to deploy its machinery to ensure the non-occurrence of such acts also constitutes a serious violation (General comment Art 2 CAT, 2008). Sexual and gender-based violence as a crime under international law enjoins states to enact legislation, if not already done so, the duty to investigate, and, if there is sufficient evidence, the duty to submit to prosecution the person allegedly responsible for the violation and, or extradite and if, found guilty, the duty to punish the perpetrator and the provides remedies such as reparation, free access to justice, free services including shelters and medical care. Despite this pronouncement, the position of victims of gross human rights violations remains largely unexplored in terms of legal remedies under international law. Not only does international law require that appropriate measures should be taken to protect victims, but it also requires that victims be provided with 'equal and

effective access to justice', adequate, effective, and prompt reparation for the harm suffered, and 'access to relevant information concerning the violation and reparation mechanism'. Adequate, effective, and prompt reparation is intended to promote justice for victims of sexual and gender-based violence. The dictum on reparation implies that such redress must be proportional to the gravity of the violations. The reparation systems may take various forms, including restitution, compensation, or satisfaction, and must be made in full (Art. 34 ILC, 2001). Without prejudice to the appropriateness of some of these reparation forms for the crime of sexual violence, it is suggested that a single or a combination of the reparation forms is possible. The international law of reparation prioritises restitution among the forms of reparation (Evans, 2012). It is only when it is not materially possible and does not put an additional burden on the victim that the state may consider other forms of reparation, including compensation. However, some scholars viewed restitution as inappropriate in the context of sexual and gender-based violence and prioritised compensation and satisfaction (Ní Aoláin, 2015). Thus, whether single or combined, reparation measures need to be determined on a case-by-case basis. Therefore, the application of states' obligations arising from the rules of international humanitarian or human rights law has no boundaries. This understanding flows directly from the impact of contemporary rules and the normative character of customary international law. Contemporary human rights rules have transcended what has always been considered the "reserved domain" of states (Benhabib, 2013). The status of international law regarding states' sovereignty claims has become a highly contentious theoretical and political issue. The universalisation of human rights norms is viewed either as a threat or as neocolonialism's intention to assert imperial control over the state. Such a view may not be accepted by all but a simplistic analysis of Article 75 (2b) of the Protocol Additional (AP) I to Geneva Conventions and Article 1(j) of the Maputo Protocol means that the protection afforded by International Humanitarian Law extends at all times and to all women, no matter their status whether prisoners of war or free in the hand of the government (Evans, 2012). Likewise, it cannot be disputed that the harm felt by women assaulted in a private space is not different from the harm felt by those assaulted during an International or Non-international armed conflict or that there is no difference between the harm suffered by women in times of peace and that of women in wartime. More prominently, there is the recognition of individual rights of action to seek compensation for violations of international humanitarian and treaty law and a lack of recognition of the status of limitation of the crimes of sexual and gender-based violence. Even peace treaties concluded at the end of WWII could not exhaust the legal rights of victims of sexual slavery because of the *erga omnes* nature of crimes against humanity.

Conclusion

The international legal framework addressing state responsibility and remedies for sexual and gender-based violence has evolved into a sophisticated and comprehensive system that establishes binding obligations across multiple legal regimes while providing various mechanisms for accountability and redress. The convergence of human rights law, international criminal law, international humanitarian law, and sanctions regimes creates overlapping and mutually reinforcing obligations that significantly strengthen the

legal foundation for addressing SGBV at both national and international levels.

The development of the content and scope of such obligations, whether under national or international law, must be guided by widely accepted jurisprudence and foundational principles in judicial reasoning. Notably, the SERAC case and the UN's Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law serve as essential frameworks for understanding the substantive and operational dimensions of states' positive obligations. However, significant challenges remain in translating these legal obligations into effective protection and meaningful remedies for survivors. The effectiveness of international legal frameworks ultimately depends on domestic implementation, adequate resource allocation, and sustained political commitment at the national level. Future developments in this area will likely focus on strengthening implementation mechanisms, improving coordination between different legal regimes, and ensuring that legal obligations translate into tangible improvements in prevention, protection, and accountability for sexual and gender-based violence.

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